

1 Neural correlates of human fear conditioning and sources of variability in 2199 individuals

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ABSTRACT

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Pavlovian fear conditioning is a fundamental process in both health and disease. We investigated its neural correlates and sources of variability using harmonized functional magnetic resonance imaging data from 2,199 individuals across nine countries, including 1,888 healthy individuals and 311 with anxiety-related or depressive disorders. Using mega-analysis and normative modeling, we show that fear conditioning consistently engages brain regions within the "central autonomic–interoceptive" or "salience" network. Several task variables strongly modulate activity in these regions, contributing to variability in neural responses. Additionally, brain activation patterns differ between healthy individuals and those with anxiety-related or depressive disorders, with distinct profiles characterizing specific disorders such as post-traumatic stress disorder and obsessive-compulsive disorder. While the neural correlates of fear conditioning are highly generalizable at the population level, variability arises from differences in task design and clinical status, highlighting the importance of methodological diversity in capturing fear learning mechanisms.

149 **INTRODUCTION**

150 Fear conditioning, also known as threat conditioning, is a psychological paradigm developed
151 over a century ago to study associative learning mechanisms. It remains one of the most
152 widely used and productive experimental models for investigating both normal and
153 pathological fear and anxiety in humans¹. Fear conditioning models how the association
154 between an initially neutral stimulus (conditioned stimulus, CS) and an innately aversive
155 stimulus (unconditioned stimulus, US) is learned. The success of learning in fear conditioning
156 is typically assessed by comparing responses to the fear cue (CS+, paired with the US) and
157 the safety cue (CS-, not paired with the US) across subjective, autonomic, or neural domains.
158 Successful conditioning is indicated by greater responses to the CS+ than to the CS-². In the
159 brain, this involves activity changes within a “central autonomic–interoceptive” or “salience”
160 network, which in humans includes functionally and anatomically connected regions like the
161 dorsal anterior cingulate cortex (dACC) and the anterior insular cortex (AIC)³. Additionally,
162 fear conditioning has been linked to decreased activity in regions like the ventromedial
163 prefrontal cortex (vmPFC), although such decreases have been less extensively studied³.
164 Although the amygdala plays a crucial role in fear conditioning in rodents^{4–6}, and classical
165 lesion studies have implicated the amygdala in human fear conditioning⁷, this relationship has
166 not been consistently identified in human fMRI studies^{3,8–12}.

167 Limitations in prior research on the neural correlates of human fear conditioning
168 include the use of small sample sizes (typically $n < 30$) and the reliance on heterogeneous
169 neuroimaging processing and analytical methods^{3,13}. While group-level meta-analyses can
170 partially address the sample size issue³, individual-level *mega-analyses* offer additional
171 advantages. These include enhanced statistical power, more precise effect size estimation,
172 standardized preprocessing and analysis techniques, and substantially improved power to
173 detect whether activation is modulated by individual variability -one of the primary goals of
174 the current study^{14–16}.

175 Individual differences, such as sociodemographic factors (e.g., age) and trait variables
176 (e.g., trait anxiety), are likely to modulate the neural correlates of fear conditioning,
177 potentially affecting the generalizability of findings across groups, such as younger versus
178 older adults or individuals with high versus low anxiety¹³. However, existing research on
179 individual differences has been inconsistent and often hampered by limited sample sizes
180 ($n < 50$ ¹³) or sampling biases¹⁷. Moreover, task-specific variables, such as task instructions or

181 characteristics of the US, may also influence conditioning at the behavioral or neural level
182 ^{2,13,18,19}. For example, compared to other USs, a tactile electric shock may elicit greater
183 activation in the dACC and the ventral supplementary motor area³. A primary challenge in
184 this field is integrating prior data to accurately assess how individual differences and task
185 variables affect neural outcomes. This complexity arises from variations in adjustable factors
186 and sampling across studies and participants, highlighting the need for methods that can
187 account for and isolate specific sources of variation—such as the normative modeling
188 approach used here. Normative modeling allows us to integrate multiple smaller-scale studies
189 into a common reference space—a standardised baseline against which to statistically
190 quantify individual variations. This approach allows for meaningful comparisons across
191 diverse studies by controlling for multiple sources of variation. As a result, the variance
192 associated with specific variables and individuals can be isolated, quantified, and
193 systematically analysed²⁰. (For details on the underlying mathematics, see references ²¹⁻²³; for
194 applications, see ²⁴⁻²⁹).

195 Fear conditioning has also been used to study the development and persistence of
196 mental health disorders marked by pathological fear, such as anxiety-related disorders^{1,30-33},
197 which are highly prevalent and rank among the leading causes of disability worldwide³³.
198 However, there is ongoing debate over whether anxiety-related disorders consistently show
199 abnormal fear conditioning at behavioral or neural levels^{34,35} or if these abnormalities are
200 specific to certain clinical groups—such as post-traumatic stress disorder (PTSD³⁶) but not
201 others, like social anxiety disorder (SAD)³⁷. Inconsistencies maybe due in part to small
202 sample sizes (ns<100 for anxiety-related disorders as a group, ns<25 for comparisons among
203 clinical groups). Furthermore, most research in this area has relied on case-control designs
204 and traditional analysis techniques, both of which have limitations that could be addressed
205 through normative modeling. This framework enables statistical inference for individual
206 subjects relative to an expected population pattern, providing a more detailed examination of
207 the heterogeneity underlying group-level analyses²⁰.

208 In this study with pre-registered hypotheses and analyses (cf. **Materials and**
209 **Methods**), we used both mega-analysis and normative modelling to analyse individual-level,
210 harmonized fMRI data acquired during fear-conditioning from 43 samples from 21
211 laboratories across 9 countries (total n=2199), including both healthy participants and
212 individuals diagnosed with anxiety-related and depressive disorders. First, we assessed the
213 overall neural correlates of fear conditioning in healthy participants to provide a

214 comprehensive delineation of the brain regions underlying human fear conditioning. Based
215 on previous studies, we hypothesized that during fear conditioning, the CS+>CS- contrast
216 would be associated with robust activations in regions such as the dACC, AIC,
217 pre/supplementary motor areas, and dorsolateral prefrontal cortex (dlPFC), whereas the
218 CS+<CS- contrast would be associated with deactivations in the vmPFC and hippocampus.
219 We expected the mega-analysis to be more sensitive than previous studies in detecting subtle
220 effects in other brain regions not previously (or not consistently) identified. Second, we
221 assessed variation among healthy participants. Given their role in mediating subjective
222 arousal and autonomic expression of fear³⁸, we hypothesised that regions including the
223 vmPFC and the anterior-to-mid cingulate cortex would show the greatest between-subject
224 heterogeneity. Third, we examined how individual differences (e.g., age, trait anxiety) and
225 task variables (e.g., task instructions) influenced this variation. Finally, we explored
226 differences in the neural correlates of fear conditioning between individuals with anxiety-
227 related and depressive disorders and healthy controls, as well as among clinical subgroups
228 (e.g., PTSD, SAD). We show that fear conditioning is consistently associated with brain
229 activation in regions of the central autonomic-interoceptive network, despite methodological
230 variations. However, specific task variables also influence the responses of these regions
231 during conditioning. Additionally, brain activation patterns during conditioning differ
232 between healthy individuals and those with anxiety-related or depressive disorders, with
233 certain groups displaying distinct activation profiles.

234

235 **RESULTS**

236 All results -including effect sizes for the linear models- are available in a free open-access
237 repository (see **Data availability statement**).

238 *Conditioning is associated with extensive brain (de)activations*

239 In the mega-analysis (**Fig. 1a**), we included data from 1888 healthy
240 individuals (42 experiment samples) and used linear mixed-effect
241 models (LMMs) to perform a mega-analysis of whole-brain
242 activation during fear conditioning (CS+>CS- contrast). We
243 observed significant activation encompassing clusters within the
244 bilateral anterior and mid insular cortices; the secondary

245 somatosensory cortices (SII); the dlPFC; the lateral premotor
246 cortices; and the dorsal and lateral cerebellum (**Fig. 1b**). Significant
247 activation was also observed in multiple regions across the cortical midline, including the
248 dACC extending to the pre-supplementary and supplementary motor areas (SMA), ventral
249 posterior cingulate cortex, and dorsal precuneus (dPrec).

250 Additionally, the CS+>CS- mega-analysis revealed the broad activation of subcortical
251 regions, particularly the thalamus and basal ganglia. The largest of these activation patterns
252 were observed in the dorsal striatum, specifically the caudate nucleus (CN); the globus
253 pallidus extending to the striatum; the ventral tegmental area extending to the habenula; the
254 mediodorsal thalamus (Thal); and the midbrain tegmentum. Activation of the midbrain was
255 noted generally across the dorsal midbrain (~substantia nigra/red nucleus and pretectal
256 nuclei) (**Supplementary Fig. S1**). To specifically assess the role of the amygdala, we
257 conducted a Region of Interest (ROI) mega-analysis focusing on this region (see **Materials**
258 **and Methods**), which indicated that neither the left ($t = 1.93$, $p = 0.054$, Cohen's $d = 0.129$,
259 95% CI [-0.002, 0.260]) nor the right amygdala ($t = 1.57$, $p = 0.116$, Cohen's $d = 0.117$, 95%
260 CI [-0.029, 0.264]) showed significant activation during fear conditioning.

261 We also observed significant deactivations (CS+<CS- contrast) during fear
262 conditioning, predominantly in regions of the default mode network (**Fig. 1c**). This included
263 the posterior cingulate cortex (PCC) and precuneus; the vmPFC extending to the mPFC and
264 subgenual cingulate cortex medially, as well as the left dorsal prefrontal cortex (dPFC); the
265 bilateral angular gyri; and the parahippocampi and hippocampi (Hipp). Additional
266 deactivation was observed in the lateral orbitofrontal cortex; the primary somatosensory
267 cortex (SI); as well as the left temporal (TG) and fusiform gyri (see **Supplementary Fig. S2**
268 for detailed activation and deactivation across axial, sagittal, and coronal slices).

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270 *Heterogeneity in the neural correlates of conditioning*

271 We estimated voxel-wise normative models of fear-conditioning related activation using the
272 CS+>CS- contrast from 894 controls (training sample), and specifying age, biological sex,
273 sample, and task variables as covariates (see **Materials and Methods** for all variables. The
274 normative modeling sample is smaller than the mega-analysis due to the requirement for
275 participants to have data on all covariates used in model construction). Testing these models
276 with a held-out test sample ($n=646$) showed good model fit with explained variance reaching
277 0.3 in regions that showed activation during fear conditioning (**Fig. 1b**), and skew and

278 kurtosis within acceptable limits (**Supplementary Fig. S3**). For each participant in our held-
279 out test sample, we then calculated a deviation score (z-score) within each voxel. In other
280 words, for each participant, we quantified the distance from the predicted mean activation of
281 each voxel, relative to the normative reference distribution for that voxel (**Fig. 1d**). While
282 almost every voxel had at least 5 participants with large deviations (deviations $>\pm 2.6$),
283 including areas such as the bilateral insula and expanses of the cingulate cortex extending to
284 the medial prefrontal cortex (**Supplementary Fig. S4**), controls most frequently had large
285 deviations (both positive and negative) within the most ventral region of the vmPFC and
286 inferior temporal pole. As this ventral region is notoriously prone to signal drop out, we
287 interpret this result as most likely reflecting varying signal intensity rather than individual
288 differences, and thus chose to interpret deviations within this region with caution (**Fig. 1e**).
289

290 *Individual differences have small associations with conditioning*

291 We examined the role of the following individual differences variables using LMMs and
292 normative models (**Fig 1a**): age, biological sex, and self-reported trait anxiety and depressive
293 symptoms. In normative models, we analyzed both regression coefficients, reflecting each
294 variable's contribution to the regression equation, and structure coefficients, indicating the
295 direct bivariate relationship between a variable and brain activity without accounting for
296 other predictors.

297 In LMMs, age (n=1884 controls) and biological sex (n=1888 controls) showed a
298 significant association with brain activation or deactivation during fear conditioning
299 (**Supplementary Fig. S5**). However, the effect sizes were small (**Supplementary**
300 **Discussion**). Additionally, the age range was restricted (see **Table 1**). Regression and
301 structure coefficients also showed minimal effects of age and biological sex (n=646 controls)
302 (**Supplementary Fig. S5**). Neither trait anxiety (n=1402 controls), using either harmonised or
303 non-harmonised scores (**Supplementary Methods**), nor depressive symptoms (n=213
304 controls) were significantly associated with brain activation or deactivation during fear
305 conditioning in LMMs. Similarly, elastic net regressions showed that whole-brain deviation
306 scores derived from normative models could not explain the variance in individual levels of
307 trait anxiety (n = 751 controls and cases; $r^2 = -0.095$, $p = 0.459$), nor depressive symptoms
308 (n = 152 controls and cases; $r^2 = -0.257$, $p = 0.605$). See **Methods** for a note on negative r^2
309 values and **Supplementary Table S1** for trait anxiety and depressive symptoms scores.

310

311 ***Task variables have a robust effect on conditioning***

312 The influence of task variables on brain activation during fear conditioning was also
313 examined using LMMs and structure coefficients from normative models in healthy controls.
314 Several task variables were associated with robust effects across individuals, showing at least
315 moderate effect sizes in LMMs and reaching significance in normative modeling analyses.
316 These included instructions given to the participant about contingency prior to the task, the
317 type of US, the use of a paradigm with multiple CSs (i.e., more than one CS+ or CS-), the
318 pairing rate (i.e., percentage of CS+ followed by a US), and potential US confounding (i.e.
319 whether trials followed by the US were included in the CS+ vs CS- contrast, and therefore the
320 effects of the US may confound the effects of the CS+).

321 Partial instructions about CS-US contingency (n=1388) were associated with
322 significantly increased activation in the supplementary motor area and superior parietal
323 lobule compared to no instructions about contingency (n=500) in LMMs. Structure
324 coefficients from the normative models (n=646) showed that partial instructions (as
325 compared to no instructions) produced a model predicting more activation in the bilateral
326 anterior insula, the thalamus, the left caudate, clusters within the dorsomedial prefrontal
327 cortex, the dorsolateral precuneus, and in the posterior region of the vmPFC. The model also
328 predicted less activation within the bilateral visual cortex, the anterior medial temporal gyrus,
329 and in the anterior vmPFC with the use of partial instructions (**Figure 2a**). Note that we
330 excluded instructed conditioning studies (**Materials and Methods**).

331 Compared with an auditory US (n=337), a tactile electric shock US (n=1472)
332 produced significantly greater activation in bilateral dorsal mid-insula, dorsal medial
333 thalamus, and pre-supplementary motor area, extending to the dACC (n=337) in LMMs. In
334 normative modelling analyses, a tactile electric shock US predicted increased activation
335 within the dACC extending to the pre-supplementary motor area, the dorsal precuneus,
336 secondary somatosensory cortex, the bilateral dorsal mid- to- posterior insula, the midbrain
337 and pons, and the superior cerebellum, and less activation (i.e., more deactivation) within an
338 expanse of the vmPFC, and SI. Moreover, the use of an auditory US was significantly
339 associated with increased activation in the left auditory cortex and was predictive of
340 increased activation in the bilateral auditory cortex (superior temporal lobe) and less
341 deactivation (i.e., more differential activation) within an expanse of the vmPFC extending to
342 the dorsomedial prefrontal cortex, posterior cingulate cortex, angular gyrus, and SI (**Figure**
343 **2b**).

344 In LMMs, compared to paradigms with a single CS+ (n=1283), paradigms with
345 multiple CS+ (n=605) produced increased activation in the left supplementary motor area
346 (SMA) and left dorsal precuneus and widespread increased deactivation in regions including
347 the bilateral temporal poles, the right parahippocampal gyrus extending to the fusiform gyrus,
348 the left visual association cortex extending to the angular gyrus, and the right primary motor
349 and somatosensory cortex. Comparing paradigms with multiple CS- (n=302) and those with a
350 single CS- (n=1586) revealed identical regions with increased activation to paradigms with
351 multiple CS+. Conversely, increased deactivation was shown in the bilateral anterior
352 hippocampus, ventral PCC, primary motor and somatosensory cortex, precuneus, and right
353 mid-insula. In normative models, this was modelled using two variables (multiple CS+ and
354 multiple CS-). Multiple CS+ predicted less activation within the bilateral amygdala, a
355 bilateral expanse of SI the angular gyrus, the posterior cingulate cortex, the bilateral putamen
356 and caudate, and the lingual gyrus. Similarly, multiple CS- predicted decreased activation
357 within a bilateral expanse of SI and the lingual gyrus (**Figure 2c**).

358 Pairing rate, treated as a continuous variable, did not relate to brain activation during
359 conditioning in LMMs. However, due to the non-normal distribution of pairing rates across
360 studies and individuals, we categorized pairing rates (e.g., 30%, 50%, and 100%) and
361 conducted ANOVA-like LLMs followed by pairwise comparisons with Holm-Bonferroni
362 correction, which revealed significant effects (**Figure 2d**). In particular, the comparisons
363 involving the 50% pairing rate category was the category where significant differences
364 between categories occurred most frequently. The significant differences between the pairing
365 rate categories occurred both with (**Supplementary Fig. S6**) and without (**Supplementary**
366 **Fig. S7**) US confounding. The structure coefficients for pairing rate (as a linear association),
367 showed that a higher pairing rate predicted greater activation within visual regions (calcarine,
368 lingual gyrus and cuneus), the precuneus, the left dorsolateral prefrontal cortex, the superior
369 gyrus of the temporal lobe, and (less deactivation of) an anterior region of the vmPFC.
370 Conversely, a higher pairing rate predicted less activation within the mid-cingulate cortex, the
371 bilateral anterior insula, a posterior region of the vmPFC as well as the thalamus and caudate
372 (**Figure 2d**).

373 Finally, potential US confounding (n = 997), compared to no confounding (n = 891),
374 was associated with significantly increased widespread activation during fear conditioning
375 (CS+ > CS- contrast). This activation was observed across the bilateral fusiform and lingual
376 gyri, temporal poles, angular gyri, posterior insula, primary motor cortex, retrosplenial cortex

377 (extending to the posterior hippocampus), and right amygdala, predominantly in the
378 superficial amygdala, in linear mixed models (LMMs). Similarly, structure coefficients from
379 the normative models showed that the model predicted greater activation within the bilateral
380 mid-cingulate cortex extending to the dorsomedial prefrontal cortex and pre-supplementary
381 motor area, angular gyri, mid-to-posterior insula, superior temporal gyrus and temporal poles,
382 fusiform gyri and lateral mid-occipital gyrus, amygdala, caudate, dorsal thalamus, and
383 dorsolateral cerebellum with potential US confounding (**Figure 2e**).

384 None of the above results were affected by excessive multicollinearity, except for the
385 association between pairing rate and the potential US confound (**Supplementary Tables S2-**
386 **S5**). We identified six small clusters where the effects of both variables overlapped. To
387 further disentangle their contributions, we conducted mixed-effects models within these
388 clusters, including both variables as predictors. Results indicated that both variables exerted
389 statistically significant effects in all clusters except for one small cluster in the right middle
390 occipital region, where the effect of the US confound was no longer significant. Given the
391 absence of multicollinearity (Variance Inflation Factor= 1.8), we concluded that activation in
392 this region is specifically modulated by the pairing rate, rather than by the US confound.

393 The remaining task variables (for example, the number of trials during
394 preconditioning) showed weaker effects or were not significantly associated with brain
395 (de)activation during conditioning in the mega-analysis or normative modelling analyses
396 (**Supplementary Figs. S8 and S9 and Supplementary Discussion**).

397

398 *Cases and controls show differences in conditioning*

399 In the mega-analysis, individuals with anxiety-related and depressive disorders (cases,
400 n=311) showed significantly increased activation in the right ventrolateral prefrontal cortex
401 (anterior pars orbitalis), dorsal frontal pole, posterior cingulate cortex, left temporal pole, and
402 bilateral primary motor areas compared to controls (n=1888) (**Fig. 3a**). Similar results were
403 found when comparing individuals with anxiety-related disorders (i.e., excluding major
404 depressive disorder; remaining n=297) and controls, with additional clusters observed in the
405 dorsal prefrontal cortex, visual association cortex, and primary somatosensory cortex
406 (**Supplementary Fig. S10**). After excluding individuals who were taking medication at the
407 time of the scan (**Supplementary Table S6**), those with anxiety-related and depressive
408 disorders (n=221) still showed significantly increased activation in the dorsal medial
409 prefrontal cortex, dorsal PCC extending to the superior parietal lobule, left medial TG and
410 bilateral ventrolateral prefrontal cortex compared to controls (**Supplementary Fig. S11**).

411 In normative modelling, we tested our clinical test sample (260 controls + 222 cases)
412 against our reference normative models. This analysis compared the individuals' deviation
413 scores (z-score) within each voxel, and quantified, as a percentage of the sample, the
414 frequency of participants with large positive or large negative deviations (**Fig. 3b**). We
415 compared the frequency of extreme deviations throughout the whole brain (Normative
416 Probability Maps thresholded at $> \pm 2.6$), and found that cases had, on average, a greater
417 frequency of extreme deviations than controls (Mann Whitney U-test = 111167.5, $p = 0.014$;
418 **Fig. 3c**). Qualitatively, cases showed a different pattern of deviation frequency than controls.
419 Large deviations (i.e., more activity than would be predicted by the model) were common
420 across cases within the dorsomedial prefrontal cortex, the primary somatomotor cortex,
421 precuneus, the bilateral primary visual cortex (medial occipital lobe extending to the inferior
422 medial and inferior lateral lobe) extending to the lingual and fusiform gyrus. As with
423 controls, cases frequently had large negative deviations within the most ventral region of the
424 vmPFC.

425

426 *PTSD and OCD show distinct activation patterns and deviations*

427 We divided our patient sample by primary diagnosis (PTSD, $n = 141$; OCD, $n = 68$; GAD,
428 $n = 48$; and SAD, $n = 31$; other diagnoses were not included due to small sample size).
429 ANOVA-like LMMs indicated that there were significant differences in brain activation
430 during conditioning among patient groups. Post-hoc pairwise comparisons corrected for
431 multiple comparisons showed that the most significant differences occurred between
432 individuals with PTSD and OCD with respect to individuals with GAD and SAD
433 (**Supplementary Fig. S12**).

434 Similarly, normative modelling analyses identified a significant difference in the
435 frequency of large deviations among patient groups (Kruskal-Wallis H-test = 71.529,
436 $p = 1.984 \times 10^{-13}$; **Fig. 3c**). Follow-up Mann Whitney U-test's (FDR corrected for multiple
437 comparisons) clarified, for example, that extreme deviations occurred most frequently in
438 individuals with PTSD, as compared to other disorders, followed by OCD. We then
439 illustrated the location of these extreme deviations at the voxel level to determine whether
440 they were spatially overlapping within and between patient groups (**Fig. 3d** and
441 **Supplementary Fig. S13**). Individuals with PTSD showed frequent large positive deviations
442 within the bilateral medial occipital lobe extending to the inferior temporal lobe and lingual

443 gyrus, bilateral vlPFC, an expanse of the dmPFC, precuneus, and bilateral amygdala. They
444 also showed frequent large negative deviations within an expanse of the vmPFC (posterior
445 vmPFC focus), precuneus, and a focus of the lingual gyrus and fusiform gyrus. There were
446 very few regions wherein individuals with GAD showed overlapping large deviations, and
447 similarly for SAD except for a small region of the bilateral lingual gyrus frequently found to
448 have large positive deviations. Individuals with OCD showed frequent large deviations within
449 the inferior parietal cortex, and temporal pole.

450 A support vector machine could not classify cases from controls better than chance
451 using whole-brain deviation maps (mean AUC = 0.44, $p = 1.0$, 95% CI [0.30 0.58]).
452 However, a multi-class support vector classifier confirmed a unique pattern of deviations
453 among cases (**Fig. 3e**). More specifically, PTSD, on average, was accurately classified
454 54.55% of the time (mean F1 score = 0.58; $p = 2.06 \times 10^{-23}$, balanced accuracy = 0.43 where
455 chance level across 4 classes = 0.25). Interestingly, despite fewer overlapping extreme
456 deviations within the OCD group, the classifier was able to accurately label individuals with
457 OCD 73.74% of the time (mean F1 score: 0.57; $p = 1.71 \times 10^{-7}$, 95% CI [0.54, 0.60]). GAD
458 and SAD were only accurately classified 31.78% (mean F1 score: 0.35) and 13.33% (mean
459 F1 score: 0.17) of the time, respectively, and were often misclassified as OCD. The mean
460 voxel-wise coefficient weights and frequency of contribution (in penalised permutations) to
461 this classification are displayed in **Supplementary Fig. S14**.

462

463 *Sample size for future studies*

464 We conducted a series of sample size analyses to guide the design of future fMRI fear-
465 conditioning studies (**Supplementary Methods**). To detect activation or deactivation in 50%
466 of the brain regions identified in the mega-analysis (based on the AAL atlas³⁹), a sample size
467 of 122 was required, while detecting 80% of these regions required 243 participants
468 (**Supplementary Figure S15**). When considering activations only, the required sample sizes
469 were slightly smaller: 100 participants to detect 50% and 199 participants to detect 80% of
470 the mega-analytical findings. In contrast, substantially larger samples were needed to detect
471 deactivations. 263 for 50% detection and 522 for 80%. The overall false positive rate was 9%,
472 and 8% and 3% when activations and deactivations were assessed separately, averaging 5%.
473 Additional sample sizes results are presented in **Supplementary Figures S16-S18**.

474

475

476 *Early and late conditioning*

477 Given the importance of accounting for temporal dynamics in brain activity during human
478 fear conditioning⁸, we compared neural activation during the early and late phases of
479 conditioning in a subset of participants (n = 634 controls; **Supplementary Table S8**).

480 Consistent with the effects observed across the entire task, both phases showed significant
481 activation in the CS+>CS- contrast across several brain regions. These included the insular
482 cortices, SII, dlPFC, lateral premotor cortices, dorsal and lateral cerebellum, dACC extending
483 to the pre-supplementary motor area and SMA, and the dPrec (**Supplementary Figure S19**).

484 Notably, there were several significant differences between the phases. The early phase
485 showed greater activation in the bilateral fusiform gyrus, SMA, right amygdala, left frontal
486 eye fields, and left motor cortex compared to the late phase (**Supplementary Figure S19**).

487 Additionally, significant differences were also observed in the left angular gyrus; dorsal,
488 medial, and ventral anterior prefrontal cortices; and lateral orbitofrontal cortex. However, as
489 these regions were implicated in the CS+<CS- contrast, this suggests that they exhibited
490 reduced deactivation during the late phase.

491

492 **DISCUSSION**

493 We compiled the largest (n=2199) sample of individual-level fear conditioning fMRI data to
494 date to comprehensively delineate the neural correlates of human fear conditioning, to assess
495 the influence of several relevant sources of variation - including individual differences and
496 task variables- and to evaluate potential differences in fear conditioning at the neural level
497 between individuals with anxiety-related and depressive disorders and controls.

498 Our individual-level mega-analysis mapped fear conditioning activation to the
499 “central autonomic–interoceptive” or “salience” network. As hypothesised, fear conditioning
500 was associated with robust activations in the anterior insula, ventral striatum, pre-
501 supplementary /supplementary motor areas, dorsal anterior cingulate cortex, and dorsolateral
502 prefrontal cortex. It was also associated with activation in several subcortical regions,

503 particularly the thalamus and basal ganglia. While many of the observed effects replicated
504 previous findings³, the increased statistical power provided by our analyses suggests that
505 peak effects in the dorsal midbrain may originate in the substantia nigra/red nucleus and
506 pretectal nuclei. Future work with a specific focus on these nuclei may aid in disentangling
507 their specific contributions to fear conditioning. Also as hypothesised, fear conditioning was
508 associated with robust deactivations in the ventromedial prefrontal cortex and hippocampus.
509 Other brain regions that were deactivated during conditioning included primarily regions of
510 the default mode network (e.g., posterior cingulate cortex and precuneus).

511 By incorporating a large sample from multiple laboratories worldwide, our study
512 underscores the generalizability of the neural correlates of conditioning at the population
513 level. At the same time, the methodological diversity across laboratories and studies suggests
514 that our findings extend beyond specific experimental conditions, reinforcing their relevance
515 to the broader fear conditioning process. Notably, at a time when neuroimaging research is
516 increasingly emphasizing sample sizes in the thousands⁴⁰, our analyses show that studies with
517 100 participants can still reliably detect the neural correlates of fear conditioning, at least
518 when considering activations only. Furthermore, our findings highlight that a significant
519 source of variability in neural responses during fear conditioning stems from differences in
520 task design. This insight is crucial for future human fMRI studies, as it enables researchers to
521 anticipate the expected effects of various task and contrast design choices, along with their
522 magnitudes, at the neural level. By making these adjustments in advance, researchers can
523 strike a balance between the advantages of large, standardized studies and those of smaller
524 studies with greater methodological diversity. Moreover, our normative modeling results
525 underscore the potential of fear conditioning paradigms for informing the development of
526 targeted interventions. Specifically, normative models can identify brain regions with atypical
527 activation during conditioning, providing valuable guidance for interventions such as
528 neuromodulatory treatments aimed at these regions⁴¹. Additionally, by pinpointing abnormal
529 activation patterns, normative models enable clinicians to tailor treatments more precisely to
530 address these specific neural deviations.

531 The amygdala was not robustly activated during fear conditioning in either our mega-
532 analysis or ROI-based mega-analysis for the contrast averaging across all trials, consistent
533 with our previous group-level meta-analysis³. However, and in line with a recent study by
534 Wen and colleagues⁸ (n = 601, including individuals with anxiety-related disorders and

535 controls), our analysis of early versus late trials in a large subsample of participants (n=634
536 controls) revealed significantly greater activation in the right amygdala during early
537 compared to late trials.

538 Inconsistencies regarding amygdala involvement in human fMRI conditioning studies
539 have been attributed to several factors, including small sample sizes and limited anatomical
540 specificity. The amygdala consists of distinct subregions, such as the basolateral (BLA) and
541 centromedial (CMA) amygdala, and averaging responses may mask specific activations^{8,10}.
542 Moreover, the amygdala's subcortical and ventral location, its small size, and the
543 susceptibility artifacts and low signal-to-noise ratio associated with traditional imaging
544 techniques can further hinder detection of significant effects⁴⁴. Ultra-high field imaging has
545 been shown to reduce these limitations and allows for more precise investigation of amygdala
546 subnuclei^{45,46}, making it a valuable tool for future human fear conditioning studies.

547 Taken together with the findings of Wen and colleagues, our results highlight the
548 importance of considering temporal dynamics when assessing amygdala activity during fear
549 conditioning⁸. Specifically, they confirm that amygdala activation is strongest during early
550 trials and habituates thereafter^{42,43}, suggesting that averaging across all conditioning trials
551 may obscure these effects. In the current study, we also identified specific task features- such
552 as the use of paradigms with multiple CS+ stimuli or US-related confounds- and diagnostic
553 categories (e.g., PTSD; see also³⁶) that modulate amygdala activity during conditioning.
554 These findings underscore that both clinical and task-related variables may also contribute to
555 the inconsistencies observed in the literature.

556 Biological sex had only minor effects, suggesting that fear conditioning mechanisms
557 are relatively stable at the neural level between sexes. Additionally, none of our analyses
558 found significant associations between brain activation during conditioning and levels of trait
559 anxiety or depressive symptoms. While some mental health frameworks suggest that
560 dimensional constructs of psychopathology, like trait anxiety, may better reflect neural
561 activation patterns⁴⁷, the variability and complexity in the neural states underlying these
562 constructs and their lack of direct mapping to neural processes makes it challenging to
563 identify clear linear relationships^{48,49}.

564 The brain activation differences during conditioning between individuals with
565 anxiety-related and depressive disorders and healthy controls, observed in the mega-analysis,

566 aligned with normative modeling results, showing a higher frequency of large deviations in
567 cases. Importantly, these differences remained significant even after excluding medicated
568 cases, suggesting that the observed effects are not due to medication. This is crucial, as
569 commonly used treatments like selective serotonin reuptake inhibitors (SSRIs) can influence
570 brain activation patterns observed with fMRI⁵⁰. When the analysis was limited to anxiety-
571 related disorders, significant differences in brain activation persisted, indicating that
572 individuals with pathological anxiety are characterized by abnormal neural responses during
573 fear conditioning. These findings suggest that such abnormalities could eventually serve as
574 neural markers for anxiety-related disorders^{51,52}.

575 Among individuals with anxiety-related disorders, those with PTSD and OCD showed
576 distinct patterns of brain activation and had distinct patterns of voxel-wise deviations that can
577 be used to distinguish them from other anxiety-related disorders. This provides
578 neurobiological support for the decision of current diagnostic classifications to separate these
579 conditions⁵³. In addition, it may provide new insights into the underlying mechanisms of
580 psychopathology. The sample of individuals with PTSD was still relatively heterogeneous,
581 with data from three independent samples, and yet there were often overlapping extreme
582 positive deviations. Furthermore, using the derived deviation scores we were able to
583 differentiate and classify individuals with PTSD and OCD with striking precision, compared
584 to GAD and SAD. This is consistent with the previous literature that used mean averaging
585 methods and reported differences in activation levels between groups of individuals with
586 PTSD, compared to controls^{36,54}. Taken together, this suggests that the neural mechanisms
587 engaged during a fear conditioning paradigm are specifically relevant to the psychopathology
588 of, and to some extent, similarly altered across individuals with PTSD; reinforcing the notion
589 that fear conditioning is a foundational process in PTSD psychopathology, and as such,
590 related tasks are a useful clinical model³¹. The accurate differentiation of OCD, despite few
591 regions of overlapping large deviations, appeared to be driven by consistent coefficient
592 weights with a region of the bilateral superior temporal gyrus and right vIPFC. Combined
593 with no strong behavioural evidence⁵⁵, mixed imaging evidence of differences in fear
594 conditioning tasks in this population⁵⁶⁻⁵⁹, and evidence of altered baseline activity within the
595 superior temporal region⁶⁰, this finding may be interpreted as capturing compensatory
596 mechanisms that individuals with OCD engage to overcome obsessions and achieve the same
597 behavioural output^{55,60,61}. Despite significant differences in the frequency of extreme
598 deviations between individuals with GAD and SAD compared to controls, their limited

599 spatial overlap and less accurate classifications, suggest that there is significant heterogeneity
600 in fear conditioning among individuals with these diagnoses. Thus, while we suggest that the
601 psychopathology of PTSD is uniquely related to fear or threat processing as captured by fear
602 conditioning tasks, we propose that other anxiety-related disorders, particularly GAD and
603 SAD are less so.

604 Our study has several limitations. First, despite using harmonized pre-processing
605 pipelines and statistical models to account for site differences, variations in diagnostic
606 routines and imaging acquisition contributed to sample heterogeneity, particularly among
607 individuals with anxiety and depressive disorders (a label that includes already heterogenous
608 disorders). Second, mega-analyses may have limited power to detect effects in small
609 subgroups (e.g., SAD patients). Third, for participants with a mental health diagnosis, we
610 focused on primary diagnoses and we could not assess (or control for) comorbidity. Fourth,
611 while our normative models adjusted for site, age, biological sex, and task influences on brain
612 activity, future studies should explore the impact of adding more variables in the model
613 construction. It is possible that alternative model structures could have increased the
614 explained variance in the relatively noisy BOLD activation (where other literature has
615 explained up to 51.3% of the variance²⁵). However, care must be taken not to overfit or
616 reduce the generalisability of models to ensure their wider utility. Fifth, we were unable to
617 include other individual-level measures of conditioning (e.g., psychophysiological data) in
618 our analyses, as this would have required separate collection and harmonization procedures.
619 Finally, cross-sectional data on brain activation during fear conditioning raises concerns
620 about the reliability of outcome measures. Although fMRI-based fear conditioning shows
621 limited test-retest reliability at the whole-brain level, significant within-subject similarity
622 across repeated time points has been observed⁶², suggesting that large test-retest samples
623 could help further validate the normative modeling approach, as demonstrated in other
624 tasks²⁵.

625 With this work, we provide the largest analysis of the neural correlates of human fear
626 conditioning and potential sources of variation to date. Our results confirm that human fear
627 conditioning is a robust phenomenon at the neural level, consistently engaging multiple brain
628 regions within the central autonomic-interoceptive or salience network. Our comprehensive
629 review of the influence of task design choices on elicited and predicted brain activation can
630 be used to help interpret differences in the previous literature and should remind researchers

631 of the potentially significant influence of task design choices. Finally, we found that there are
632 overall differences in fear conditioning at the neural level between individuals with anxiety-
633 related and depressive disorders and controls, and that a unique mechanism of PTSD
634 psychopathology is well captured by fear conditioning paradigms, supporting the use of these
635 models to study this disorder.

636

637

638

639 **METHODS**

640 The current manuscript combines two pre-registered analyses of individual-level fear
641 conditioning fMRI data (<https://osf.io/7n953>; <https://osf.io/w74bt>). Data were collated from
642 43 samples originating from 23 sites in 9 countries. Collation was coordinated by the lead
643 group (IDIBAPS Barcelona). ENIGMA Fear Conditioning is part of the larger ENIGMA-
644 Anxiety Working Group⁶³. **Table 1** and **Table 3** summarize the descriptive information on
645 the samples. Informed consent was obtained from all participants by the sites providing their
646 data. Some site-specific data have been reported previously, but no reports have examined all
647 individual data together.

648

649 **Fear conditioning task**

650 We included data from participants who completed a fear conditioning experiment during an
651 fMRI scan. There are several human fear conditioning paradigms, which vary based on the
652 time elapsed between the CS and the US (e.g., delay, trace, simultaneous, or backward
653 conditioning), the use of one (single-cue) versus two or more (differential-cue) CSs, and the
654 instructions given to participants²: 1) *No instructions*: For example, “During this experiment,
655 you will see various images and might experience mild electric shocks at certain times”; 2)
656 *Partial instructions*: For example, “During this experiment, you may see a particular image
657 sometimes followed by a mild electric shock. However, the shock won’t happen every time
658 you see the image, and sometimes it might not appear at all. Pay attention to the images, as
659 they might give you some indication of when the shock could occur”; 3) *Full instructions*
660 (instructed conditioning): For example, “During this experiment, you will see the image X,
661 which is always followed by a mild electric shock. Whenever this image appears, it will be
662 followed by the shock shortly afterward. No other images will be associated with the shock”.

663 We focused on delay differential cue-conditioning paradigms with no or partial
664 instructions (i.e., excluded instructed conditioning studies), and focused our analysis on
665 comparing the response to a CS+ compared to a CS-. **Table 2** summarises information on the
666 fear conditioning tasks included in this manuscript.

667

668 **Non-imaging data: sociodemographics and individual differences**

669 All sites were asked to provide information regarding sociodemographics (age, biological
670 sex) and individual differences: trait anxiety, assessed with the Trait subscale of the State-

671 Trait Anxiety Inventory (STAI-T)⁶⁴; and depressive symptoms, assessed with the Beck
672 Depression Inventory (BDI)⁶⁵ (**Supplementary Table S1**). For individuals with anxiety-
673 related and depressive disorders, sites were asked about principal mental health diagnosis and
674 psychotropic medication use at the time of the scan (**Supplementary Table S6**). Previous
675 normative studies of trait anxiety (STAI-T) have shown additive and multiplicative
676 differences across countries, for which we harmonised trait anxiety scores across countries
677 using ComBat¹⁴ (**Supplementary Methods**) and conducted subsequent analyses twice: once
678 with the raw scores and once with the country-harmonised scores.

679

680 **Non-imaging data: task-related variables**

681 We collected information about the following task variables: instructions given to the
682 participant about contingency prior to the task (partial versus no information); type of US
683 (e.g., electric shock versus aversive sound); number of trials during pre-conditioning; use of a
684 paradigm with multiple CSs (i.e., more than one CS+ or CS-) during conditioning; type of CS
685 (e.g. geometrical figures, faces, etc); number of CS+ and CS- trials during conditioning;
686 average ITI (inter-trial interval); average ISI (inter-stimulus interval, i.e., between the CS+
687 and the US); pairing rate (percentage of CS+ followed by a US); potential US confounding;
688 and the number of CS+ trials and CS- trials included in the fMRI contrast. For studies
689 assessing awareness (conscious recognition of the association between the CS+ and the US,
690 after the task), we also asked about participant's contingency awareness (yes vs. no). Task
691 variables were not explicitly listed in the pre-registration. The decision to include these
692 variables was based on previous research^{2,13}.

693

694 **Processing of neuroimaging data**

695 We included only neuroimaging data acquired with whole-brain coverage. Individual-
696 level raw task-based fMRI data were processed using the Harmonized Analysis of Functional
697 MRI pipeline (HALFpipe, version 1.2.2)⁶⁶, a tool developed within the ENIGMA consortium
698 to harmonise fMRI analyses across sites and facilitate reproducible analyses. HALFpipe
699 provides a standardised workflow that extends fMRIPrep⁶⁷ with several additional
700 preprocessing steps, including spatial smoothing, grand mean scaling, temporal filtering, and
701 confound regression. Moreover, HALFpipe generates a standardised quality assessment of
702 the preprocessing outputs and imaging raw data (**Supplementary Table S7**). We used
703 HALFPIPE default parameters (smoothing using 6mm FWHM; confound removals using
704 ICA-AROMA; and a high-pass filter of 125 s).

705 For the current study, each site was provided with a comprehensive manual to
706 perform image pre-processing and quality control with HALFpipe in a fully harmonised
707 manner, and each group shared the HALFPIPE output files for each individual along with the
708 non-imaging data for each individual. The lead group (IDIBAPS-Barcelona) processed 5
709 sites, aggregated all the data, and carried out additional quality control procedures and
710 measures to ensure the comparability of the data, as described in the **Supplementary**
711 **Methods**).

712

713 **Statistical analyses**

714 We conducted two types of statistical analyses: mega-analyses and normative
715 modelling analyses.

716

717 *Mega-analyses*

718 **Participants**

719 We included data from 2199 participants (M_Age=25.26, SD=5.47; 57.2% female),
720 comprising 1888 healthy controls (M_Age=25.85, SD=8.51; 51.53 % female) and 311
721 individuals with a primary diagnosis of an anxiety-related or depressive disorder
722 (M_Age=29.91, SD=10.75; 58.84 % female) (**Table 1** and **Table 3**). Diagnoses were
723 established with structured clinical interviews.

724

725 **Pre-scaling**

726 Although we used the exact same processing protocol and conducted extensive quality
727 control (see above), we observed differences in the BOLD response between samples, most
728 likely due to varying units of measurement (note that MRI scans are acquired in arbitrary
729 units⁶⁸. To address these differences, we pre-scaled the images for healthy controls so that,
730 for each sample, the voxel-wise-median standard deviation (after removing the effects of
731 covariates) was 1 (see **Supplementary Methods**). We then applied the pre-scaling
732 parameters obtained from the healthy controls to the cases (individuals with a primary
733 diagnosis of an anxiety-related or depressive disorder). This approach differs from using the
734 individual z-statistic images (i.e., dividing the BOLD response by its standard error), which
735 we did not adopt for the mega-analysis. The reason is that the standard error may differ
736 between cases and controls, and thus, differences in z-statistics between groups could reflect

737 differences in the standard error rather than in the BOLD response (for more details, see
738 **Supplementary Methods**).

739

740 **Analyses**

741 Differences in brain coverage across sites prevented us from using the standard ComBat
742 method, which determines the harmonisation parameters using all voxels¹⁴. Additionally,
743 there was no need to remove differences in scaling because we had already pre-scaled the
744 images as described above. Thus, we used LMMs (with the sample as a random intercept) to
745 investigate: 1st the pattern of brain activation during fear conditioning in healthy controls and
746 in cases (individuals with anxiety-related and depressive disorders), which tested whether the
747 mean activation in each voxel was non-null; 2nd the pattern of differences in brain activation
748 during fear conditioning between cases and controls, which tested whether activation in each
749 voxel was different between cases and controls; 3rd the pattern of differences in brain
750 activation during fear conditioning among patient groups (PTSD, OCD, GAD, SAD), testing
751 whether activation in each voxel differed among patient groups; 4th the potential influence
752 of individual differences and task variables (see above) on brain activation during fear
753 conditioning in healthy controls, which tested whether activation in each voxel was
754 significantly associated with each task variable. In all models, we incorporated age and sex as
755 covariates. Significant LMMs comparing three or more groups (analog to ANOVAs) were
756 followed by pairwise comparisons with Holm-Bonferroni correction.

757 We also conducted an ROI mega-analysis focusing on the amygdala. For this analysis, we
758 extracted the pre-scaled BOLD response in the left and right amygdala based on the
759 Automated Anatomical Labeling atlas³⁹. We used an LMM, with age and sex as covariates, to
760 test whether the mean activation significantly differed from zero. Potential differences
761 between early and late conditioning were also analyzed using a LMM, with age and sex as
762 covariates in a subsample of controls (n=679; **Supplementary Table S8**).

763 We fitted the LMMs using custom functions (included in 'combat.enigma' R
764 package) that call the 'nlme' R package voxel-wise and address voxel-specific details (e.g.,
765 varying collinearity due to differing brain coverage; see **Supplementary Methods**). FSL was
766 then used to derive cluster-based corrected p-values using Gaussian Random Field (GRF)
767 theory.

768

769

770 **Analyses of multicollinearity**

771 Given the diverse range of variables examined in this study—many of which may be
772 influenced by methodological factors (e.g., pairing rate, type of conditioned stimuli) or
773 sample characteristics (e.g., patient vs. control group)—there is a potential risk of
774 confounding. That is, the observed effects attributed to one task variable may partially or
775 wholly reflect the influence of another. To address this possibility, we systematically assessed
776 interrelationships among all methodological and clinical variables using correlation analysis
777 and evaluated multicollinearity using variance inflation factors (VIF). For pairs of variables
778 with correlation coefficients exceeding 0.5 (or eta and Cramér's V when involving categorical
779 variables), we further examined whether their associated activation maps exhibited spatial
780 overlap. Overlap was defined as clusters of at least 10 contiguous voxels showing significant
781 activation for both task contrasts. This approach was guided by the rationale that classical
782 confounding requires both variables to be associated with activation in the same brain region.
783 For any pair of correlated variables with overlapping activation, we re-estimated the mixed-
784 effects linear models within the overlapping clusters, this time including both variables as
785 predictors, to determine whether their effects remained statistically significant. A reduction to
786 non-significance upon joint inclusion could indicate either collinearity (as suggested by the
787 VIF) or potential confounding.

788

789 **Effect sizes**

790 To compare the effect sizes of different variables and to exclude findings with negligible or
791 very small effects, we converted the regression coefficients of the peaks into correlation
792 coefficients (Pearson r). For variables comparing two groups (e.g., cases vs. controls), we
793 also calculated the corresponding standardised mean differences (Cohen's d). We considered
794 effects with $r < 0.2$ (roughly equivalent to $d < 0.4$ for balanced binary variables) to be small, and
795 only highlighted larger effects (i.e., $r > 0.2$, i.e., at least moderate) in the main text. It is
796 important to note that peak effect sizes should be interpreted with caution, as they correspond
797 to the peaks of clusters of statistical significance and are, therefore, larger than those obtained
798 by other methods. Effect sizes for all the LMMs can be found at
799 <https://figshare.com/s/d44cc1390711bad3c147>

800

801 *Normative modelling analyses*

802 **Participants**

803 We included data from 2022 participants; 1800 healthy controls (age range 8-66 years, mean
804 age: 25.66 ± 8.4 , 53.05% female) and 222 individuals with anxiety-related and depressive
805 disorders (age range 9-63, mean age: 28.27 ± 11.06 , 54.95% female) to build and test the
806 normative models. See **Table 1** note to explain discrepancy in participant numbers from
807 mega-analysis.

808 **Generating Normative Models of Activation to the CS+ > CS- contrast**

809 The z-statistic maps (files) from the CS+ > CS- contrast for each participant were used as
810 inputs (response variables) for the normative models. We created a normative model of fear-
811 related activation per voxel, as a function of age, sex, and task variables (the same reported in
812 the **Non-imaging data: task-related variables** section, except contingency awareness) by
813 training a Gaussian Bayesian Linear Regression (BLR) model to predict activation for the
814 CS+ > CS- contrast²². We included dummy coded site-related variables (sample, and MR
815 strength) and a b-spline basis expansion as additional covariates of no-interest. This was
816 performed in the Predictive Clinical Neuroscience toolkit (PCNtoolkit) software v0.26
817 (<https://pcntoolkit.readthedocs.io/en/latest>) implemented in python 3.8. Generalisability was
818 assessed by using a stratified train-test sample (train: 894, control test sample: 646).

819

820 **Quantifying voxel-wise deviations from the normative model**

821 To estimate a pattern of regional deviations from typical brain function for each participant in
822 the control test sample (n = 646, mean age: 25.45 ± 7.19 years, 52.16% female), we derived a
823 normative probability map (NPM) that quantifies the voxel-wise deviation from the
824 normative model. The subject-specific Z-score indicates the difference between the predicted
825 activation and true activation scaled by the prediction variance. This was repeated for the
826 clinical test sample (n = 482, 260 controls + 222 cases, mean age: 26.76 ± 10.94 years,
827 54.97% female). We thresholded participant's NPM at $Z = \pm 2.6$ (i.e., $p < .005$) as in previous
828 work⁶⁹⁻⁷¹ and summed the number of significantly deviating voxels for each participant.
829 Kruskal-Wallis H-tests were used to test for group (cases or controls) and diagnosis effects

830 and, when applicable, follow-up Mann Whitney U-tests were False Discovery Rate (FDR)⁷²
831 corrected at $\alpha = 0.05$.

832

833 **Normative models: individual differences and task variables**

834 **Model Coefficients:** To probe the magnitude of the influence of individual differences
835 (sociodemographics) and task variables on the predicted brain activation, we examined both
836 the regression coefficients and the structure coefficients (correlation coefficients) of all
837 sociodemographic and task variables input variables. Structure coefficients are preferable to
838 regression coefficients when variables are collinear⁷³. Note that negative R^2 values
839 (“negative” explained variance) is a possible outcome when the model fails to generalize
840 effectively to new data, despite in-sample performance yielding non-negative explained
841 variance (which is always positive or zero by construction). This phenomenon is not
842 uncommon and arises when the model's predictions result in a residual sum of squares that
843 exceeds the variance of the true values.

844 **Linear Regression (Elastic Net) and Support Vector Classification (SVC):** We applied an
845 elastic net linear regression as implemented in the scikit-learn package (version 1.0.2)⁷⁴ with
846 10 repeats of nested 5-fold cross validation [alphas = 0.0001, 0.001, 0.01, 0.1, 0.3, 0.5, 0.7, 1;
847 90% train, 10% test split] to predict trait anxiety as measured by the STAI-T ($n = 751$), or
848 depressive symptoms as measured by the BDI ($n = 440$) from participants' whole brain
849 (unthresholded) deviation maps. The mean coefficient values and the frequency of the
850 voxel's contribution (in other words, how many of the cross-folds split found this voxel to be
851 important) indicate which voxel contributed to the prediction. The statistical significance of
852 these results was tested against a 1000-fold nested 5-fold test for each variable. To classify
853 participants ($n = 703$) who were contingency aware from those who were not based on their
854 unthresholded whole-brain deviation maps, we used an SVC model with a linear kernel,
855 regularisation parameter set to 1.0, and balanced class weights as implemented in the scikit-
856 learn package (version 1.0.2).

857

858 **Quantifying patterns of deviations between cases and controls**

859 To classify individuals with anxiety-related or mood disorders and controls based on their
860 whole brain unthresholded deviation maps, we used a SVC model with a linear kernel,
861 regularisation parameter set to 1.0, as is common in neuroimaging, and balanced class

862 weights (i.e. adjusted inversely proportional to class frequencies in the input data) as
863 implemented in the scikit-learn package (version 1.0.2)⁷⁴. The evaluation metric for the
864 classification is area under the receiving operator curve (AUC) averaged across all folds
865 within a 10-fold cross validation framework.

866 **Quantifying patterns of deviations among patient groups**

867 We used a one versus rest support vector classifier (SVC OvR) model as implemented in the
868 scikit-learn package (sklearn.multiclass.OneVsRestClassifier version 1.0.2) to determine if
869 there were quantifiably differentiable patterns within the whole brain unthresholded deviation
870 maps among patient groups. Due to the small number of individuals with major depressive
871 disorder (n = 11), specific phobia (n=7) and panic disorder (n=2), this analysis only included
872 individuals with a diagnosis of PTSD (n=55), OCD (n=68), GAD (n=48) and SAD (n=31)
873 (total n = 202). The model classes were the participants' diagnosis. The evaluation metric for
874 the classification was the F1-metric (the harmonic mean of precision and recall, also known
875 as the balanced F-score, where values closer to 1 indicate greater classification success) per
876 class within a 5-fold cross-validation framework, and the statistical significance was tested
877 against a 1000-fold nested 5-fold test.

878

879 **Data availability statement**

880 All results from this manuscript can be found at
881 <https://figshare.com/s/d44cc1390711bad3c147>

882 The ENIGMA-Fear Conditioning Group (part of the ENIGMA-Anxiety Working Group⁶³ is
883 open to sharing the individual-level data (HALFIPE results files) from this investigation to
884 researchers for secondary data analysis. To request access to data, an analysis plan can be
885 submitted to the ENIGMA-Anxiety Working Group
886 (<http://enigma.ini.usc.edu/ongoing/enigma-anxiety/>). Data access is contingent on approval
887 by PIs from contributing samples.

888 **Code availability statement**

889 All code to reproduce the analyses in this manuscript is available at:
890 <https://figshare.com/s/d44cc1390711bad3c147>. The functions needed to conduct the mega-
891 analysis are also included in the ‘combat.enigma’ R package.

892

893 **Table 1.** Descriptive statistics for all samples (N=43) included in the analyses.

894

Sample	Country	N	Sex (%females)	Healthy Controls (n)	Patients (n)	Age M (SD) Range (min-max)	Years of education M (SD) Range (min-max)
Amsterdam_Visser/Kindt__sample_1	NL	18	72	18	0	22.06 (3.35) 18-31	not available
Amsterdam_Visser/Kindt__sample_2	NL	41	73	41	0	20.56 (1.79) 18-24	not available
Amsterdam_Visser/Kindt__sample_3	NL	12	75	12	0	21 (1.35) 19-23	not available
Amsterdam_Visser/Kindt__sample_4	NL	10	80	10	0	22.8 (2.04) 20-26	not available
Amsterdam_Visser/Kindt__sample_5	NL	13	85	13	0	22.23 (4.07) 19-35	not available
Amsterdam_Visser/Kindt__sample_6	NL	14	79	14	0	23.43 (2.71) 18-29	not available
Amsterdam_Visser/Kindt__sample_7	NL	16	44	16	0	24.06 (3.36) 18-29	not available
Amsterdam_Visser/Kindt__sample_8	NL	9	100	9	0	20.33 (1.41) 18-22	not available
Amsterdam_Visser/Kindt__sample_9	NL	38	58	38	0	23.66 (3.78) 18-33	not available
Austin_Cisler	US	61	100	0	61	33.72 (8.48) 21-50	15.46 (2.64) 10-22
Barcelona_Cardoner	SP	71	66	45	26	22.66 (4.67) 18-40	14.49 (2.15) 12-20
Barcelona_Soriano_sample_1	SP	35	51	17	18	37.43 (10.54) 19-58	14.69 (3.72) 6-18
Barcelona_Soriano_sample_2	SP	147	50	122	25	24.76 (4.22) 19-36	18.63 (3.95) 13-26
Bielefeld_Lonsdorf_sample_1	GE	116	66	116	0	24.61 (3.61) 18-34	15.26 (2.14) 1-16
Bielefeld_Lonsdorf_sample_2	GE	80	56	80	0	24.88 (3.51) 19-34	not available
Bielefeld_Lonsdorf_sample_3	GE	28	64	28	0	24.68 (4.95) 18-39	13.36 (1.75) 11-20
Bochum_Elsenbruch	GE	29	48	29	0	26.45 (3.59) 19-33	17.45 (4.02) 3-23

Bochum_Merz_sample_1	GE	59	49	59	0	23.88 (4.17) 18-34	16.07 (3.4) 9-26
Bochum_Merz_sample_2	GE	59	47	59	0	24.39 (3.83) 18-35	15.86 (3.72) 5-23
Bochum_Merz_sample_3	GE	47	49	47	0	22.87 (2.61) 19-30	not available
Bochum_Merz_sample_4	GE	29	0	29	0	24.21 (3.62) 19-33	not available
Bochum_Merz_sample_5	GE	31	0	31	0	24.71 (3.87) 20-34	not available
Bochum_Merz_sample_6	GE	60	50	60	0	23.57 (2.95) 18-33	not available
Columbia_Neria	US	95	46	65	30	35.65 (12.26) 18-60	15.11 (2.45) 10-24
Duke_LaBar_sample_1	US	38	47	38	0	24.68 (4.2) 19-35	not available
Duke_LaBar_sample_2	US	37	49	37	0	29.16 (11.07) 19-66	not available
Florida_Keil	US	14	36	14	0	19.79 (2.08) 18-26	14 (0) 14-14
Harvard_McLaughlin	US	89	55	75	14	13.06 (2.6) 8-17	7.04 (2.32) 2-10
Manitoba_Greening_sample_1	CA	13	38	13	0	24 (5.07) 19-36	17.15 (3.02) 14-23
Manitoba_Greening_sample_2	CA	31	55	31	0	24.23 (4.56) 17-33	not available
Melbourne_Harrison	AU	112	61	75	37	20.88 (2.34) 16-25	15.02 (2.21) 11-21
Munich_Koch	GE	45	56	23	22	34.47 (12.39) 20-63	not available
Munster_Moeck_sample_1	GE	42	69	42	0	26.02 (6.22) 19-51	12.33 (1.37) 7-15
Munster_Moeck_sample_2	GE	29	52	29	0	15.79 (0.98) 14-17	10.64 (0.99) 8-12
Reading_Reekum_sample_1	UK	21	57	21	0	24 (2.59) 21-31	not available
Reading_Reekum_sample_2	UK	50	60	50	0	17.8 (3.46) 12-25	11.34 (1.82) 8-14
MGH_Tuominen_sample_1	US	14	0	14	0	36.36 (9.61) 22-49	15.69 (1.84) 12-19

MGH_Tuominen_sample_2	US	37	43	37	0	28.51 (5.81) 19-42	17.08 (2.27) 12-23
USP_Diniz	BR	55	58	27	28	35.56 (10.97) 19-63	13.13 (4.1) 1-17
Texas_Dunsmoor	US	45	64	23	22	23.47 (4.51) 18-37	NA
Ulm_Abler	GE	50	0	50	0	22.6 (2.92) 18-29	NA
Uppsala_Ahs	SW	278	58	278	0	33.87 (10) 20-58	14.16 (1.65) 9-15
Vanderbilt_Kaczurkin	US	81	0	53	28	33.47 (9.7) 19-61	15.74 (2.18) 13-20
Total n/Mean (SD)/Range		2199	52.69	1888	311	25.26 (5.47) 8-66	14.53 (2.56) 1-26

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896 AU, Australia; BR, Brazil; CA, Canada; GE, Germany; NA, Not available; NL, The Netherlands; SP, Spain; SW, Sweden; UK, United Kingdom, US, United
897 States. Note: To be included in the normative modelling analysis each participant had to have all essential data (age, sex) available, samples had to have
898 control participants and larger samples required both genders available. These reasons lead to the exclusion of the entire Austin_Cisler and
899 Vanderbilt_Kaczurkin datasets, as well as 7 additional participants. The Bielefeld_Lonsdorf_sample_3 was not approved for inclusion in the normative
900 modelling analysis. Thus, a total of 177 fewer participants were included in the normative modelling analysis.

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911 **Table 2.** Characteristics of the fear conditioning tasks for each sample.

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Sample	CS+/ CS- (n/n)	CS+ trials (n)	CS- trials (n)	Average ITI (ms)	Average ISI (ms)	Pairing rate (%)	CS type	Type of US	US confound	Assessment of awareness	Preconditioning phase
Amsterdam_Visser/Kindt__sample_1	2/2	22	22	22000	6000	55	Neutral faces & pictures	Electric shock	no	yes	yes
Amsterdam_Visser/Kindt__sample_2	2/2	22	22	20000	4000	55	Neutral faces & pictures	Electric shock	no	yes	yes
Amsterdam_Visser/Kindt__sample_3	2/2	18	18	17500	4000	56	Neutral faces & pictures	Electric shock	no	yes	yes
Amsterdam_Visser/Kindt__sample_4	2/2	18	18	17500	4000	56	Neutral faces & pictures	Electric shock	no	yes	yes
Amsterdam_Visser/Kindt__sample_5	2/2	18	18	10350	4000	56	Neutral faces & pictures	Electric shock	no	yes	yes
Amsterdam_Visser/Kindt__sample_6	2/2	18	18	10350	4000	56	Neutral faces & pictures	Electric shock	no	yes	yes
Amsterdam_Visser/Kindt__sample_7	2/2	18	18	4650	4000	56	Neutral faces & pictures	Electric shock	no	yes	yes
Amsterdam_Visser/Kindt__sample_8	2/2	18	18	17500	4000	56	Neutral faces & pictures	Electric shock	no	yes	yes
Amsterdam_Visser/Kindt__sample_9	2/2	22	22	20000	4000	55	Neutral faces & pictures	Electric shock	no	yes	yes
Austin_Cisler	1/1	18	18	4000	2500	50	Neutral pictures	Electric shock	no	yes	yes

Barcelona_Cardoner	1/1	32	32	5891	1900	50	Neutral pictures	Auditory stimulus	no	yes	yes
Barcelona_Soriano_sample_1	2/1	16	16	15000	5800	62.5	Neutral pictures	Electric shock	yes	yes	yes
Barcelona_Soriano_sample_2	1/1	15	10	12000	1750	33	Neutral pictures	Electric shock	no	yes	yes
Bielefeld_Lonsdorf_sample_1	1/1	14	14	13000	6800	100	Neutral pictures	Electric shock	yes	yes	yes
Bielefeld_Lonsdorf_sample_2	1/1	14	14	13000	7000	100	Neutral pictures	Electric shock	yes	no	yes
Bielefeld_Lonsdorf_sample_3	2/2	18	18	10000	7000	100	Grey fractals	Electric shock	yes	yes	yes
Bochum_Elsenbruch	1/1	8	8	25000	9000	100	Neutral pictures	Other*	yes	yes	no
Bochum_Merz_sample_1	2/1	16	8	10750	8000	62.5	Neutral pictures	Electric shock	no	yes	no
Bochum_Merz_sample_2	2/1	16	8	10750	8000	62.5	Neutral pictures	Electric shock	no	yes	no
Bochum_Merz_sample_3	1/1	21	21	12000	8000	100	Neutral pictures	Electric shock	yes	yes	no
Bochum_Merz_sample_4	2/1	16	8	10062	6000	62.5	Neutral pictures	Electric shock	no	yes	no
Bochum_Merz_sample_5	1/1	16	16	10750	8000	62.5	Neutral pictures	Electric shock	no	yes	no

Bochum_Merz_sample_6	2/1	16	8	10062	6000	62.5	Neutral pictures	Electric shock	no	yes	no
Columbia_Neria	1/2	15	30	3600	4000	80	Neutral pictures	Electric shock	yes	no	yes
Duke_LaBar_sample_1	2/2	20	20	5750	6000	50	Avatars with neutral faces	Electric shock	yes	no	yes
Duke_LaBar_sample_2	1/1	16	16	15900	4000	31	VR affective pictures	Electric shock	yes	no	yes
Florida_Keil	1/1	29	20	7000	5100	25	Gabor patches	Electric shock	yes	yes	yes
Harvard_McLaughlin	1/1	8	4	20000	1500	40	Neutral pictures	Auditory stimulus	no	no	no
Manitoba_Greening_sample_1	1/1	24	24	12000	6000	50	Gabor patches	Electric shock	no	no	yes
Manitoba_Greening_sample_2	1/1	24	24	12000	3995	50	Gabor patches	Electric shock	no	no	yes
Melbourne_Harrison	1/1	15	10	12000	1950	33	Neutral pictures	Auditory stimulus	no	yes	yes
Munich_Koch	1/1	8	8	12000	12000	50	Affective faces and pictures	Electric shock	yes	no	no
Munster_Moeck_sample_1	1/1	27	27	5750	300	33	Neutral faces	Auditory stimulus	no	yes	yes
Munster_Moeck_sample_2	1/1	27	27	5750	300	33	Neutral faces	Auditory stimulus	no	yes	yes

Reading_Reekum_sample_1	1/1	12	12	10530	500	100	Neutral pictures	Auditory stimulus	yes	no	no
Reading_Reekum_sample_2	1/1	12	12	10530	500	100	Neutral pictures	Auditory stimulus	yes	no	no
MGH_Tuominen_sample_1	2/1	16	16	15000	6000	62.5	Neutral pictures	Electric shock	yes	no	no
MGH_Tuominen_sample_2	1/1	8	8	15000	6000	62.5	Neutral faces	Electric shock	yes	no	no
USP_Diniz	2/1	16	16	15000	3000	62.5	Neutral pictures	Electric shock	yes	yes	no
Texas_Dunsmoor	1/1	24	24	6000	5000	50	Other**	Electric shock	yes	no	no
Ulm_Abler	2/1	80	20	variable	2500	50	Neutral pictures	Thermal stimulus	no	no	no
Uppshala_Ahs	1/1	16	16	14000	6000	50	Humanoid characters	Electric shock	yes	yes	yes
Vanderbilt_Kaczurkin	2/1	15	30	3600	3900	80	Neutral pictures	Electric shock	yes	yes	yes

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914 CS, conditioned stimulus; CS+, CS followed by unconditioned stimulus; CS -, CS not followed by unconditioned
915 stimulus; CS+/CS-, Number of different CS+ and CS-; ITI, intertrial interval; ISI, inter-stimulus interval;
916 US=Unconditioned stimulus. All samples used visual conditioned stimuli. All samples included an independent
917 assessment of conditioning (e.g., skin conductance responses) except Amsterdam_Visser/Kindt_1. For all samples,
918 the fMRI contrast (CS+ > CS-) included either all CS+ trials (with US present) or all CS+ trials without the US,
919 along with all CS- trials. Exceptions included Barcelona_Cardoner, Duke_LaBar_sample_1, and

920 Duke_LaBar_sample_2, which only included trials from an early conditioning phase (n = 4CS+/4CS-, 5CS+/5CS-, and
 921 8CS+/8CS- trials, respectively). *Rectal distension. ** Typical exemplars.

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Table 3. Characteristics of individuals with anxiety-related and depressive disorders included in the analyses.

Sample	N	Age M (SD)	Females (%)	Medication (%)	Comorbidity (%)	GAD (n)	MDD (n)	OCD (n)	PTSD (n)	SAD (n)	PD (n)	SP (n)
Austin_Cisler	61	33.72 (8.48)	100	59.02	67.21	0	0	0	61	0	0	0
Barcelona_Cardoner	26	23.88 (4.78)	61.54	3.85	11.54	26	0	0	0	0	0	0
Barcelona_Soriano_sample_1	18	40.56 (11.91)	61.11	88.89	50	0	0	18	0	0	0	0
Barcelona_Soriano_sample_2	25	25.56 (3.68)	64	0	16	21	0	0	0	4	0	0
Columbia_Neria	30	35.07 (13.82)	33.33	0	80	0	0	0	30	0	0	0
Harvard_McLaughlin	14	14.57 (2.14)	50	0	0	1	0	0	3	1	2	7
Melbourne_Harrison	37	19.89 (2.31)	51.35	0	56.76	0	11	0	0	26	0	0
Munich_Koch	22	33.55 (13.59)	59.09	54.55	27.27	0	0	22	0	0	0	0
USP_Diniz	28	33.68 (8.09)	53.57	0	71.43	0	0	28	0	0	0	0
Texas_Dunsmoor	22	25.95 (5.04)	68.18	NA	0	0	0	0	22	0	0	0
Vanderbilt_Kaczurkin	28	34.57 (9.36)	0	3.57	32.14	0	3	0	25	0	0	0
Total n/M	311	29.91 (10.75)	58.84	21.22	44.05	48	14	68	141	31	2	7

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 928 Data refer to primary mental health diagnoses. "Comorbidity" refers to the presence of at least one additional mental disorder. Data on comorbidity were not
 929 included in the analyses. GAD=Generalized Anxiety Disorder, MDD=Major Depressive Disorder, NA=Not available, OCD=Obsessive-Compulsive Disorder,

930 PD=Panic Disorder; PTSD=Post-traumatic Stress Disorder, SAD=Social Anxiety Disorder; SP=Specific Phobia.

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Figure 1. Neural correlates and individual-level heterogeneity in human fear conditioning. Schematic indicating the levels of analysis (a). Significant brain functional activation (b) and deactivation (c) to the CS+ versus CS- determined by mega-analysis (n=1888 healthy controls). Schematic of normative modelling framework (d). Normative probability maps illustrate the percentage of participants in the healthy control test sample who had positive (hot colours -right) or negative deviations (cool colours - left) $\geq \pm 2.6$ within each voxel. Circle highlights frequent large deviations (both positive and negative) within the most ventral region of the vmPFC (e). Abbreviations: AIC, anterior insular cortex; AG, angular gyrus; CN, caudate nucleus; dACC, dorsal anterior cingulate cortex; dIPFC, dorsolateral prefrontal cortex; dPFC, dorsal prefrontal cortex; dPons, dorsal pons; dPrec, dorsal precuneus; Hipp, hippocampus; HYP, hypothalamus; IOFC, lateral orbitofrontal cortex; PCC, posterior cingulate cortex; SI, primary somatosensory cortex; SII, secondary somatosensory cortex; SMA, supplementary motor area; TG, temporal gyrus; Thal, thalamus; vmPFC, ventromedial prefrontal cortex.

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951 **Figure 2. Robust influence of task variables on brain activation during fear conditioning.** Maps show the influence of pre-
952 task instructions about CS-US contingency (a), type of US (b), number of CS used in paradigm (i.e. multiple CS+ or CS- or
953 single CS+ or CS-) (c), pairing rate (d), and potential US confounding in CS+ > CS- contrast (e) on mean activation (left; mega-
954 analysis linear mixed-effects models) and relation to predicted activation (right; normative model structure coefficients).

955 Structure coefficient maps show the correlation coefficients (ρ) thresholded by their respective coefficients of determination
956 ($\rho^2 > 0.3$) of selected task variables. This can be interpreted as showing how predicted activation to the CS+ > CS-
957 contrast relates to the task variables included in the building of the normative models. Positive correlations (warm colours) indicate
958 greater activation for higher values of the input variable and negative correlations (cool colours) greater activation for lower
959 values of the input variable (note that some variables are dummy coded, e.g. pre-task instructions, type of US). CS=Conditioned
960 Stimulus; US=Unconditioned Stimulus. For Pairing Rate (RR) in linear mixed-effects models, the figure shows significant results
961 in the ANOVA comparing four categories (RR30, RR50, RR62, RR100). For the results of post-hoc tests, see Supplementary
962 Figures S5 and S6.

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Figure 3. Differences between individuals with anxiety-related and depressive disorders and healthy controls in human fear conditioning. Regions wherein individuals with anxiety-related and depressive disorders (n=311) (a) showed significantly increased functional activation to the CS+ versus CS-, as compared to healthy controls. Normative probability maps illustrate the percentage of participants of the sample (test controls - top; individuals with anxiety-related and depressive disorders - bottom) who had positive (hot colours - right) or negative deviations (cool colours - left) $\geq \pm 2.6$ within each voxel (b). Box plots show frequency (median line) of the total number of large deviations ($> \pm 2.6$) per clinical group. Whiskers show ± 1.5 times interquartile range (c). Normative probability maps illustrate the percentage of each clinical group who had positive (hot colours - right) or negative deviations (cool colours - left) $\geq \pm 2.6$ within each voxel (d). Confusion matrix for multi-class support vector differentiating patterns of deviations among clinical groups (e). Abbreviations: GAD, Generalised Anxiety Disorder; OCD, Obsessive Compulsive Disorder; PTSD, Post-traumatic Stress Disorder; SAD, Social Anxiety Disorder.

982 **References**

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1184 AUTHOR CONTRIBUTIONS

1185 **J.R., H.S., E.V., and M.A.F. designed and performed analyses. J.R., H.S., A.J., and**
1186 **M.A.F. wrote the manuscript. J.M.B-H., N.A.G., D.J.S., N.J.W., J.D., A.F.M., and**
1187 **B.J.H. discussed the results. M.A.F. supervised research. All authors commented on the**
1188 **manuscript.**

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1191 COMPETING INTERESTS

1192 Dr Stein has received consultancy honoraria from Discovery Vitality, Johnson & Johnson, Kanna, L'Oreal,
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1195 **INCLUSION AND ETHICS STATEMENT**

1196 This study involved a mega-analysis of previously collected human neuroimaging datasets.
1197 All original studies received approval from their respective institutional ethics committees
1198 and were conducted in accordance with the Declaration of Helsinki. Informed consent was
1199 obtained from all participants in the original studies. Inclusion and exclusion criteria were
1200 prespecified in each dataset and applied consistently during data aggregation. Both male and
1201 female participants were included across datasets, and efforts were made to account for
1202 demographic diversity (e.g., age, sex) in the analysis. No new data were collected specifically
1203 for this study.